

USE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES BY B.ED. STUDENTS

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Abstract

Social networking sites are very effective media to get in touch with our family, friends and current important social events. No doubt it is a faster media than the news papers. Besides communication with friends, family members and entertainment social media can be effectively used for the educational purpose also. College students can form groups and can share their views, material discuss about various things. This study was undertaken in keeping a view that how many students use social networking sites for the educational purpose. For this study 200 students studying in B.Ed. colleges were studied with survey method. The research revealed that a little percentage of students use social media for the educational purpose. Most of the students use it for the purpose of entertainment and to keep in touch with friends.

Introduction-

Since their introduction, social network sites such as MySpace, Face book, Orkut and LinkedIn, twitter have attracted millions of users, many of whom have integrated these sites into their daily practices. At present there are hundreds of SNSs, with various technological affordances, supporting a wide range of interests and practices. While their key technological features are fairly consistent. With these social networking sites you can share events, photographs, videos, can share the links and other available resources from the internet. Now a day's face book is very popular social networking community among Indian youth. With this site text chatting as well as video chat is also possible.

Objectives of the Study –

- 1) To study the purpose of use of social networking sites by the B.Ed. students.

Significance of the Study –

Along with the purpose of entertainment social networking media can be used for the educational purpose also. It can be used effectively. Many more educational information can be shared with this media .B.Ed. students are prospective teachers they should be aware about the educational use. Students possess various types of learning styles with these social networking sites teachers can give justice to student's learning styles. As B.Ed. students are future teachers it is necessary to study that how these students use social networking sites.

Sample –

For the present study sample has been selected from three B.Ed. colleges. Colleges were selected with purposive method of sampling and for the selection of students from above colleges random sampling method was applied by the researcher.

Names of the Colleges are as follows –

- 1) G.E.Society's College of Education and Research ,Parel, Mumbai
- 2) Chembur Comprehensive College of Education and Research, Chembur
- 3) PVDT College of Education for women, Mumbai

200 students were selected with random method from above colleges.

Tools Used –

The researcher has developed a questioner for this study .The researcher has personally administered the questioner and collected the data.

Analysis of Data & Interpretation -

Analysis of the data revealed following facts about the use of social networking sites by the student teachers. Data has been analyzed qualitatively with simple statistics i.e. Percentage.

- 1) Among the selected sample 60% students use social networking sites. Among

- 2) these students 55% students use face book and 5% students use face book as well as Linked in.
- 3) 40% students are aware about social networking sites but they have not used it so far.

- 4) 58% students use social networking sites for the purpose of chatting with their friends.
- 5) 45% students think that it is a best media to share their photographs.
- 6) 19% students are the members of educational groups.
- 7) Only 10% students are active in uploading educational materials in respective groups they belong.
- 8) 30% students are agreed that because of chatting language proficiencies are improved.
- 9) 40% students take benefit of educational material uploaded by others.

Conclusion –

On the basis of above interpretation it is revealed that prospective teachers are not very much serious about the educational use of social networking sites. Entertainment, uploading photos and videos are the main activities on which they concentrate more.

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